

An Analysis of Transnational Ideological Influences on the Freedom Charter

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Although widely celebrated as a “people’s document” of South Africa, the Freedom Charter reflects significant influence from European ideological traditions and political thought. Rather than emerging in isolation, the Charter bears the imprint of transnational ideas that shaped its normative and philosophical foundations. The Freedom Charter arose from post-Second World War political activism, situating it firmly within the global ideological currents of its time. As resistance movements mobilised against the injustices of apartheid, there was a notable circulation of political ideas and ideological frameworks across regions and continents. This paper examines how the dominant social and ideological discourses of the period informed the conceptual orientation of the Freedom Charter, and the South African politics in general. Employing a qualitative research design, the study relies on desktop research for data collection and content analysis for data interpretation to uncover the underlying influences that shaped the document. In doing so, it highlights the complex interplay between historical context and political ideology in the formation of one of South Africa’s most influential political texts.

Keywords: Freedom charter, African national congress, South Africa, Atlantic charter

The 1955 Freedom Charter was connected to foreign or European influence through the adoption of common theories and ideologies like socialism, communism, Marxism, and liberalism. The role of international human rights agreements, such as the Atlantic Charter of 1941, in assisting third-world nations on their paths to self-determination had to be further linked. The Atlantic Charter’s consolidation by the ANC is also covered in this study. The Freedom Charter incorporated many of the tenets of the Atlantic Charter, such as self-determination, political freedom, and economic security. It further discusses ANC influence in the global political environment. The study further discusses the environmental stimulus that influenced the thinking of not only the ANC at the time but also the various groups that contributed to the founding of the Freedom Charter and the transformation of South Africa into a democracy. The environmental stimulus was a key factor that informed and inspired the ANC to embrace the ideals expressed in the Atlantic Charter (Padayachee & Van Niekerk, 2019) and later in their own Freedom Charter.

Objective of the study is to examine how the dominant social and ideological discourses of the time, informed the conceptual orientation of the Freedom Charter, and the South African politics in general. This paper is structured as follows. It begins with the method, followed by an analysis of transnational ideological influences, including key human rights documents such as the Atlantic Charter of 1941, and the African Claims, showing how global ideas informed African political thought. It also deals with the role of the United Nations and the influence of socialism in South

Africa, situating these within post-Second World War political activism. The study also explores the footprint of socialism post-1994, thereby highlighting its impact on contemporary development and policy debates. Finally, the discussion and conclusion.

Method

This study adopts a qualitative research approach to examine the social and ideological influences that shaped the Freedom Charter. A systematic review of both foundational and contemporary literature on political ideology, liberation movements, and post-Second World War activism is employed to establish the analytical context. Qualitative methodology is particularly appropriate for this inquiry, as it facilitates an in-depth interrogation of meaning, power relations, and historically embedded discourses within political texts. As argued by Creswell (2018) and Denzin et al. (2018) qualitative research is well-suited to uncovering the interpretive dimensions of social and political phenomena.

Data for the study are drawn from historical records, archival sources, and peer-reviewed scholarly literature relevant to the emergence of the Freedom Charter. In addition, elements of critical discourse analysis are employed to interrogate how power, ideology, and transnational political ideas are articulated and legitimised within the Charter. By situating the Freedom Charter within its historical and ideological milieu, the methodology foregrounds the dynamic interplay between context, discourse, and political ideology, thereby offering a nuanced understanding of the forces that shaped one of South Africa’s most influential political documents.

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Transnational Ideological Influences

Human Rights Documents

Black South Africans borrowed from and were inspired by foreign international treaties that determined their social order. The most significant effect of The Atlantic Charter of 1941 was that it laid the groundwork for a post-war settlement on a political level. This consequently had a significant impact on socialist movements and

other South African opposition political movements like the ANC. Later, in the ANC's 1943 document, African Claims, several of the important clauses from the Atlantic Charter were incorporated (Padayachee & Van Niekerk, 2019). With the ANC having founded a Bill of Rights in 1923, the documents helped lay the foundation for the principles expounded in the Freedom Charter. The Freedom Charter, however, was rather unique in that it was significantly more ambitious in terms of what it covered, its "declaratory" tone, as well as how it was created (Suttner, 2015). Noteworthy is that the Freedom Charter was not conceived by a committee of prestigious individuals, as had been the case with "African Claims" and other various international documents, nor was it intended as a document of any organisation. While there may be other international agreements that may have impacted the political direction of the ANC and South Africa, this study shall only articulate the 1923 Bill of Rights, and the 1941 Atlantic Charter.

Bill of Rights in 1923

It may be reasonable to question whether the South African Natives National Congress (SANNC), which founded the 1923 Bill of Rights, qualifies as a foreign influencing factor. The founding members of the SANNC later developed and adopted a resolution on a Bill of Rights after failing to convince Britain to have the Union recognise the rights of black South Africans after the end of World War I (Padayachee & Nieker, 2019). Former ANC president Josiah Gumede referred to the Soviet Union as a "New Jerusalem" after his visit there in the 1920s. The Soviet Union then started to gain prominence as a symbol of what was feasible in South Africa in the minds of the ANC and SACP. This means that even though the ANC produced the Bill of Rights in 1923, its members were influenced by the ideologies of the recently established Soviet Union, which African South Africans perceived as a source of moral authority. The ANC and SACP were motivated by this to push for radical political and economic change, which resulted in the adoption of socialist policies designed to create an egalitarian society for all African South Africans (Padayachee & Nieker, 2019).

This further illustrates how the Soviet Union was able to exercise a significant level of influence in South Africa, as its ideologies were embraced by the leaders of the ANC and SACP (Golan, 1987:307). The ANC and the SACP formed an alliance that saw the Soviet Union increase its communist influence in the movement struggling against institutionalised racial segregation that existed in South Africa (Golan, 1987).

As a result, the Soviet Union supported the ANC, the SACP, and many other liberation movements on the continent. The delegation that was responsible for the ANC Bill of Rights comprised of Josiah Tshangana Gumede, Thomas Levi Mvabaza, Richard Victor Selope Thema, Rev. Henry Ngcayiya, and Sol Plaatje (ANC founding members). This delegation was sent to Moscow to ensure that their efforts would be seen and acknowledged by the Soviet Union, a strong ally in the struggle against institutionalised racial segregation (Nthai, 1998). Although the document was not comprehensive, it was formulated in not so many words to express that the Bantu inhabitants of the Union have, as human beings, the indisputable right to a place of abode in this land. It demanded representation by members of their own race in all legislative bodies on the land (Nthai, 1998: 143).

The ANC used the Bill of Rights as leverage to get Union of South Africa Prime Minister Jan Smuts to acknowledge, among other

things, the rights of black South Africans. Unfortunately, the ANC's attempt was unsuccessful since not much was accomplished using the 1923 Bill of Rights as a guide (Walshe, 1970). Nevertheless, as seen by its persistence in both their historical records and the tale of the African struggle for independence in South Africa, the Bill of Rights contributed to the establishment of the ANC.

The same was observed where the Freedom Charter resembled the ideological sentiments of socialism. Basic components of socialism originated with immigrant workers from Europe and with black students who returned to school after being exposed to the Labour Movement. These workers and students were not just exposed to socialism; they had been active in the international movement of labour (Jordan, 1986). By 1945, the communists had stretched their influence among black South Africans (Fortescue, 1991:486).

In this way, they managed to imbue the Freedom Charter with socialist elements and become a major force behind the early civil rights movement. This gave the Freedom Charter a revolutionary feel and promoted socialist causes within the anti-apartheid struggle. The Freedom Charter could therefore be seen as a product of both the communist and civil rights movements.

Atlantic Charter of 1941 and the African Claims

Following the League of Nations' inability to preserve global peace, culminating in the Second World War. There emerged a pressing need for effective solutions to promote self-determination among nations worldwide. According to Borgwardt (2006), the Atlantic Charter was a product of a historic summit lasting three and a half days, held between the President of the United States and the Prime Minister of Great Britain on August 14, 1941. This crucial meeting brought together two of the world's leading democratic powers at a time when they held significant influence on the global stage, signifying the inaugural superpower summit in history (Borgwardt, 2006). The Atlantic Charter emerged as a beacon of moral guidance for nations worldwide, offering a foundational framework for governance aimed at fostering peace and security among their populations. This crucial summit was a direct response to the unbalanced political landscape of Europe during the Second World War, serving as a collective effort to address the challenges and uncertainties of the global conflict. In essence, the Atlantic Charter represented a collective commitment to shared values and principles, signalling a unified resolve to navigate the complexities of wartime dynamics and chart a course toward a more peaceful and secure future for all nations involved.

Notably, Britain drew support from its colonies, which it had subjugated. What came out of the summit was an eight-point statement of war and peace aims (Borgwardt, 2006). Immediately after it was pronounced to the world, allied nations subscribed to the Atlantic Charter, while also triggering interest from Third World countries under colonial rule. The Atlantic Charter was significant for a number of reasons even though it was not a legally binding agreement. It declared in the open that the United States and Great Britain were united in their opposition to Axis hostility (Office of the Historian, undated).

Also, the Atlantic Charter, for the first time, pronounced the prospects of a multilateral platform that would usher in the much-needed security, economic independence, self-determination, social welfare, and human rights provisions amongst other things, in the post-war epoch (Ibhawoh, 2014: 842-843). Furthermore, the Atlantic Charter envisaged a certain kind of government system

(democracy) that would resemble and establish grounds for bilateral and multilateral relations and would further be characterised by freer exchanges of trade, self-determination, disarmament, and collective security (Borgwardt, 2006).

The Atlantic Charter further served as an inspiration to all colonial subjects throughout the world, as it gave them hope for self-determination, self-government, and the protection of basic rights. It was a remarkable document that acknowledged the basic right of all people to live in freedom, dignity, and peace (Ibhawoh, 2014:843). This document was a major advancement for the cause of human rights and has been held up as a beacon of hope for people who are oppressed around the world.

It is important to keep in mind that the Atlantic Charter was originally intended to be confined to the British Empire, according to Churchill, and to only apply to countries that were occupied by Germany. When it came to the right of every country to self-determination, Churchill disagreed with the Atlantic Charter's universal applicability. Gandhi asserted in 1942 that democracy sounds hollow so long as India was excluded (Gandhi, 1942) advocating for the broader application of the Atlantic Charter. India was sending the world's largest volunteer force at the time to fight for the Allies, principally in West Asia and North Africa (Ward, 2012). Roosevelt and Churchill disputed this stance until coming to an agreement in August 1941. The formal endorsement of and the formal scope of applicability of the Atlantic Charter were formally recorded through the signing of the Declaration of the United Nations on January 1, 1942 (Willis, 2012:598).

Ibhawoh (2014) cited eight guiding principles outlined in the Declaration, which all signatories to the Atlantic Charter were required to uphold. Among these principles were the pledges to abstain from hostility, respect one another's territorial integrity and sovereignty, and advance justice and equality for all members of society. The Atlantic Charter's Preamble, which stated that "peace must be based on justice" and that all signatories should pursue justice in their respective national policies and international relations, also established the benchmark for global governance and sought to advance human rights and freedoms globally (Ibhawoh, 2014).

Although the United States gained more sway in developing effective institutions, the Atlantic Charter laid the groundwork for international agreements and contributed to the promotion of peace. This led to the creation of the UN, the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) in 1947, the independence of European colonies, NATO, and the disarmament process, all of which helped to usher in a long-lasting era of peace and advance the international system outlined in the Atlantic Charter. The Atlantic Charter had a great influence on international affairs in the twentieth century, setting the stage for sweeping changes that would shape the world to come (Borgwardt, 2006). America played a significant role in founding and directing strategic multilateral organisations during the Second World War, and as a result, it had a significant influence on the idea of a multilateral order. These organisations, such as the United Nations and NATO, provided a forum to promote international cooperation on political and economic issues, enabling the United States to project its influence around the world. America gained a significant role in the post-war international order, as it became a hegemon, taking over Britain immediately after the Second World War in 1945. When viewed through the lens of the Atlantic Charter, the collaboration between Britain and America laid the groundwork for

global engagement among nations (Borgwardt, 2006:844) therefore shaping the global currents of the post-World War II era.

United Nations (UN)

The role of the United States in ushering in the post-World War II era was pivotal in shaping the emerging international order and influencing prevailing models of governance, and its significance cannot be overstated. Immediately after the end of the Second World War, America established various multilateral institutions that sustained white dominance over people of colour. America established institutions such as the UN with 15 agencies, namely the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the World Health Organisation (WHO), and the International Labour Organisation (ILO), amongst others. Jackson provides a thorough examination of how the notion of colour-blindness, along with the idea of neutrality, was utilised by the United States to reinforce and maintain white supremacy (Jackson, 2009).

These international institutions are set up to codify the expectations and agreements between nations in a way that reflects those of the dominant white culture, thereby creating an uneven power dynamic between those who benefit from this arrangement and those who are disadvantaged by it. By relying on these international institutions to codify its expectations and agreements with other nations, the West was able to create a lopsided power dynamic in which they were able to dictate the terms of engagement while maintaining a distinct advantage (Delgado & Stefancic, 2001). In institutionalising its authority, however, the West simultaneously entrenched a universal language of rights and self-determination within the global order. The possibility of social groups demanding the universal human rights envisioned in the Freedom Charter was made possible by the earlier widespread acceptance of and adherence to the Atlantic Charter. The pursuit and negotiation of the recognition of human rights and other priorities mentioned in the Atlantic Charter were subsequently sought after by various social groups across the world. This fundamentally altered how people interacted with their governments and served as a catalyst for social groups' increased ability to assert their rights and demand a voice in how their societies are run (Ibhawoh, 2014). This acknowledgement, along with the fact that numerous governments signed the Atlantic Charter and agreed to its terms, meant that social groups had a platform on which to air their complaints.

African nations, and South Africa in particular, were largely inspired by the third point of the Atlantic Charter, which advocated for respecting the right of all peoples to choose the form of government under which they will live. Under British colonial rule, South African anticolonial activists representing South African natives in the country used the Atlantic Charter as an instrument to invoke internal autonomy and self-rule against the apartheid system of government. By citing the Atlantic Charter, they sought to highlight that their struggle was not only against British colonialism but also for their right to make decisions regarding their own form of government and to strive towards self-determination (Ibhawoh, 2014).

The ANC believed that the 1941 Atlantic Charter was too vague and needed to be adapted to meet their needs, so they tasked a selected group of Africans in South Africa to do so without outside assistance. The 28-member committee consisted of prominent figures within the ANC, such as Z.K. Matthews, a lecturer at Fort Hare College and a member of the ANC executive; R.G. Baloyi, the

organisation's treasurer general; James Arthur Calata, a priest; and the ANC secretary general. AB Xuma was elected to serve as the chair of the committee (Constitutional Hill, 1943).

The Atlantic Charter had a direct influence on the African National Congress. In their annual conference at Bloemfontein on December 4, 1943, the ANC unanimously adopted the document. Subsequently, this Bill of Rights would be used to draw up the ANC's Constitutional Guidelines for a Democratic South Africa in 1989 (Ngcukaitobi, 2017). This demonstrates the breadth of the Atlantic Charter's acceptance and its sustained relevance within the South African context. It represents an intriguing instance of American and European influences shaping the ANC's ideological orientation, underscoring the interconnectedness of global political currents during the mid-twentieth century. At the same time, it highlights the ANC's willingness to draw selectively from diverse intellectual and political traditions in advancing its struggle against apartheid. In 2017, Tembeka Ngcukaitobi reaffirmed this historical connection by commending A.B. Xuma for his role in integrating the principles of the Atlantic Charter into a seminal Bill of Rights in 1943. That same year, the ANC formally adopted the Bill of Rights, establishing it as official policy, which would later serve as a crucial instrument of leverage against the apartheid regime (Ngcukaitobi, 2017). This adoption of the Atlantic Charter by the ANC not only demonstrates its continued relevance but also highlights how intertwined American and European influences were in shaping the ANC's ideological thinking and political activism.

Socialism

Karl Marx's writings served as the foundation for the political movement known as socialism, which first emerged in the late 19th century. It demands a different economic structure from capitalism, which it views as exploitative and oppressive. In response to the changes wrought by the Industrial Revolution in Europe, socialism as a concept was created (Heywood, 2017). Through labour unions, it was adopted by South Africans as a means of protesting the difficult working conditions and exploitation of the workforce, which mainly consisted of migrant workers from Africa and Asia. Both the means of production and the means of distribution are intended to be socialised under socialism (Imlay, 2013). This focus on the socialisation of economic resources and workers' rights naturally laid the groundwork for the acceptance of African socialism in South Africa.

Black labour mixed with and interacted with immigrant workers who had been exposed to socialism. More so, Black students who had been exposed to the influences of the Labour Movement were also inspired by the ideals of socialism (Jordan, 1986: 146). This, coupled with the continuing struggle against colonial rule and racial inequality, made socialism an appealing ideology to many black South Africans. In the month of March 1946, fellow communists were instructed to set up cells in different factories and to educate all party members about the trade union movements. These facilities were used to spread Marxist-Leninist ideology and to rally workers to become active participants in the labour movement. The ideals of the Freedom Charter were influenced by this period of the labour movement, which saw a renewed effort to push for social and economic rights for the working class (Pike, 1985: 70).

Indeed, the Freedom Charter connotes Marxist thinking, with the preceding examples demonstrating this general influence on the thinking and methodologies that would be preferred by the ANC in the post-apartheid era. The Freedom Charter embodies many of the

core Marxist concepts, including the rights to work and receive fair wages, access to education for all, and a redistribution of land in the pursuit of social justice. It also promotes the idea of abolishing private property, asserting that "the mineral wealth beneath the soil, the banks, and monopoly industries shall be transferred to the ownership of the people as a whole"-an idea familiar to readers of Karl Marx. More so, the Freedom Charter expresses a clear commitment to working-class solidarity, inspired in no small part by Marxist thinking (Padayachee & Niekerk, 2019).

Socialism, in this case African socialism, was widely recognised as a viable alternative to the colonial rule of law (Imlay, 2013). Some of South Africa's leaders were also influenced by early politicians who developed the African concept of socialism, including Nyerere of Tanzania and Nkrumah, Touré, and Keita of Ghana. In this context, it is also possible to understand how the leftist sentimentality of the Freedom Charter was influenced by other African states' acceptance and adoption of socialism as an alternative to unfavourable market-based systems. Imlay (2013) posit that Africans agree that African socialism was not the opposite of or a reaction to capitalism and colonialism; rather, it was adopted as an African model of development, which later sparked interest in many Africans because it made sense to them.

This African model of socialism put emphasis on the importance of communal control and self-sufficiency, which appealed to many Africans and reinforced their cultural values. African socialism was seen as a way to bring about social and economic justice, create a self-sustaining society, and empower the African people to break free from colonial exploitation. However, the definition remains ambiguous because the concept was not invented by a single person. During the immediate post-war years, socialism began to spread among African states. The goal of European socialist countries in the 1950s was to persuade Asian and African states to join their global community (Imlay, 2013: 1129).

African socialists such as Kwame Nkrumah, Julius Nyerere, and Leopold Senghor used the concept of African socialism to advocate for an economic system that would promote the unique needs of African nations. This coincides with the period that saw the proliferation of socialism in Africa. One of the first groups to adopt socialism as a guiding principle was the ANC, which was established in 1912. This is so that they could give marginalised groups in South Africa-most notably, black workers-the tools they needed to fight against oppression. Since its founding in 1912, the ANC has been a socialist organisation in South Africa. Their core beliefs revolved around the idea that all people should have access to the same opportunities and resources regardless of race, gender, or class (Dieter, 1990: 301).

Post-Second World War Political Activism

The end of the Second World War in 1945 thus created a global climate for the investigation of radical social reform ideas of a social democratic character. As discussed previously, the acceptance of the Atlantic Charter's provision for post-war democratisation and the extension of social security to all nations under Nazi and fascist occupation made it possible for the then-Xuma-led ANC and the racialist, liberal, white ruling United Party of Smuts to agree on the necessity of fundamental social reforms in South Africa. This agreement, however, did not mean that the two sides were in complete agreement; the ANC still pressed for a more inclusive and progressive reform agenda (Padayachee & Niekerk, 2019).

Afro-European petty bourgeoisie who had received a missionary education also adopted socialism. They consequently started to criticise the capitalist systems that had kept them in a subordinate position and demand social reform from their governments (Suttner & Cronin, 2006). The movement for social change manifested itself in a number of ways, including the establishment of political parties and labour unions. These parties, which tended to be socialist in outlook, fought against colonial powers' imposition of free-market capitalism and worked to advance social welfare and workers' rights. This caliber of reformists then put forth proposals that were based on state-protected social rights of citizenship that were pioneered by the Beveridge Report, which were more inclusive social policy proposals in the United Kingdom in the 1940s. The movements for social reform across the early 20th century used this report as a model for their own efforts, ultimately leading to an expansion of public services, labour laws, and social benefits in other countries (Padayachee & Niekerk, 2019).

Socialism Footmark Post- 1994

Notably, in South Africa, the leftist politics and ideas that flourished during the national liberation struggle remain part of contemporary politics (Katsakioris & Stroh, 2021). Despite the fact that many aspects of South African society have changed since the end of apartheid, the legacy of the liberation struggle still influences current political movements. Currently, socialist movements in South Africa are pushing for government action on the socioeconomic issues that the common people face in order to further socialist objectives. Parties like the Economic Freedom Fighters (EFF), who have since contested the ANC, which looks to have embraced neoliberal policies since 1994, are included in this. There is a comprehensive discussion of the EFF as a newly established socialist party in the country and its critique of the ANC's shift from left-wing ideals towards an embrace of neoliberal economic policies. The EFF's platform of socialism can be seen as a direct reaction to the ANC's shift towards neoliberal policies, and it serves as an effective counterpoint to the ANC's alleged abandonment of its left-wing ideals.

Discussion and Conclusion

A closer analysis of the transnational ideological currents that informed the Freedom Charter situates the document within a broader global intellectual history, illuminating the intricate interplay between local resistance politics and international political thought in shaping South Africa's liberation vision. In doing so, it challenges the dominant narrative that portrays the Freedom Charter as a purely organic and internally generated "people's document." Instead, the study demonstrates that the Charter was simultaneously locally grounded and globally influenced, underscoring the dynamic circulation of political ideas across borders and their strategic adaptation within the South African context.

We have discussed the domestic and external stimuli that influenced the direction of the Freedom Charter. These encompassed a complex interplay of socio-political dynamics, economic conditions, and international pressures that collectively influenced the development and adoption of the Freedom Charter's principles. The study highlights how South African social groups and individuals drew inspiration from European ideologies to advocate for greater freedom and socioeconomic advancement. Additionally, it underscores the role of British and American influences in shaping the legal frameworks of the democratic South African government, albeit maintaining white supremacy. The study stresses the significance of the Freedom Charter

in shaping the collective aspirations of the South African people and providing a blueprint for a democratic and non-racial society. The study further highlights the lasting relevance of the Freedom Charter as a beacon of hope for an inclusive society post-1994.

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